

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF ETHICS AND THE IMPACT OF ETHICAL BEHAVIOR ON THE ACTIVITIES OF THE ENTERPRISE**Mammadli T.***University of Bamberg, Germany*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199034>**Abstract**

This article provides an analysis of the impact of ethical behavior on enterprise management. The main ethical principles and models used in modern enterprises were considered, the features of business ethics in different countries of the world were analyzed, and research on this problem was carried out.

Keywords: ethics, behavior, ethical behavior, business ethics, organizational ethics, ethical norms and values, national ethical norms, business negotiations, organizational culture.

Introduction. The relevance of the topic is due to both the increased importance of ethical behavior in the management system itself, and the importance of correctly studying the features of the formation of such behavior in enterprises.

In modern times, the development of society is more organizational in nature, the vast majority of social and personal problems are discussed and resolved while working at enterprises. Enterprises created on the basis of joint activities of people implementing a common program or goal exist and develop on the basis of certain norms, rules and procedures that change under the influence of society and culture.

Each enterprise operating in a rapidly changing economic environment needs to form a culture within the organization, regulate relations between managers and employees, and improve the management structure [Solonitsina A.A. (2020)].

Material and method. In a broad sense, ethics refers to the field of philosophical science, the object of research of which is morality. Ethics - in the field of moral culture - in the field of goodness, justice, humanity, material culture - is a large and important part of world culture, morality, which has developed over many centuries by all peoples in accordance with their ideas about beauty, order, improvement, household expediency. [Akhundova N.F. (2014)].

Currently, much attention is paid to the study of business ethics and management in order to improve the level of culture. He analyzes the relationships of business partners from the standpoint of moral assessment of the reasons for success or failure in any activity, especially in commercial and managerial.

In a broad sense, business ethics is a set of ethical principles and norms that organizations and their employees should be guided by in their activities in the field of management and production. This includes issues of various levels: ethical assessment of both domestic and foreign policy of the enterprise as a whole; moral principles of employees of the organization, that is, professional morality; [Aliyev T.F., Mejnunov R.M. (2015)].

Organizational ethics are the rules, beliefs, and values that determine how managers and employees should behave in situations where their activities can help or harm other people, both inside and outside the enterprise. Morality increases the general well-being

(happiness, health and prosperity) of individuals, groups and organizations, and sometimes the well-being of the wider external environment in which the enterprise operates, and determines the goals in which the enterprise operates and how workers should behave to achieve them [Akhundova N.F. (2014)].

Every self-respecting manager must comply with the ethical standards of the enterprise in which he works.

Consider some examples:

- When hiring, each employee, especially managers, undertakes ethical and legal obligations not to share confidential information or information representing trade secrets, even if in the future he decides to leave the organization. Similarly, if your previous worker worked for another organization, they should know they have no right to distribute their previous worker's confidential information.

- the manager of the enterprise must work with full care and responsibility in accordance with the interests of the enterprise in which he works, and expect moral values. From an ethical point of view, it is not considered normal to have the interests of an external business in order to divert a significant part of their time or attention from fulfilling their duties in the enterprise or otherwise negatively affect the activities of the enterprise.

- each manager should avoid external financial or other relations that may adversely affect the interests of the enterprise, create duality in relation to the enterprise or its interests and prevent the effective performance of its official duties, and should not lead to a conflict of interest.

- it is not allowed to accept invitations to entertainment, tourist, sports events related to work, as well as accept gifts, tickets, paid rest, personal presentations in the form of money, etc. Such actions can be considered by others as an acceptance of a certain obligation by the enterprise and involving you in a conflict of interest.

Business ethics is based on respect for the interests of not only your enterprise, but also partners, customers and society as a whole. Violation of property rights, misappropriation of confidential information, inaccurate advertising, violation of consumer freedom of choice, commercial espionage lead to deformation of market relations, increase risks and transaction costs. Unfair information provokes clients, discrimination on

the grounds of unprofessionalism and "brain tricks" distort relations in the labor market.

Buying profitable orders not on a competitive basis, but through respect, bribery or blackmail and threats also destroys the market. Therefore, to avoid all these problems, many enterprises create corporate ethical codes, in writing form the ethical principles of the corporation, the ethical values of the enterprise, the rules of conduct, the responsibility of management in relation to their employees.

Thus, based on the above, it can be said that the importance of business ethics is difficult to overestimate. It not only contributes to the formation of ethical values necessary for each person and a freer orientation of entrepreneurs in complex problems that arise when making decisions, but also allows the correct conduct and processing of the market economy and market relations in general. To do this, you need to consider and understand the basic concepts, norms and rules of business ethics when studying this issue.

Result. As a result of our research, we can note that along with material factors, ethical factors also play

an important role in regulating the activities of each enterprise. At the same time, an organizational culture formed on the basis of moral factors, ethical values and norms also plays a significant role in the efficiency of the enterprise.

Ethical training, remuneration for ethical behavior, the definition of internal ethics is a necessity of modern management, since in the presence of ethical relations, services are improved, costs are reduced, and an atmosphere of cooperation and development is formed.

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